

D8.1 LCA/LCC results for conventional technologies: baseline scenario

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Deliverable Information sheet

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Executive summary

MARBEL is an European research project that aims at developing an innovative and competitive lightweight battery with the objective to accelerate the mass market take-up of electric and hybrid vehicles.

This report is the starting point to address the specific objective number 10 of the project by conducting an initial life cycle analysis from an environmental and economic point of view for the reference scenario defined also in this report. In addition, the accomplishing of task 8.1 objectives dedicated to a unified approach & baseline scenario definition.

The reference scenario is the 95kWh (around 84 kWh useable) Audi e-Tron 55 BP battery, whose main characteristics are described in this report and they were required as inputs for the life cycle studies. General methodological aspects adjusted to the existent guidelines for the LCA and LCC are introduced in a section dedicated for that. A detailed development of the methodology to be applied to MARBEL project will be in the D8.2, however, indicators or KPIs to follow the economic and environmental behaviour of the developments and are also defined in this deliverable.

Then, the focus is shifted towards a brief discussion on the present LCA and LCC studies on the existing state-of-the-art lithium-ion batteries to help to identify key issues related to the scope definition and inventory for this preliminary assessment, as well as, to know the current context and forecast for the LIB production and impacts useful to address the sustainability of these type of batteries in MARBEL project.

Scientific literature, in particular for the battery chemistry of the reference scenario (NMC-622), was the main source for the inventory for the LCA study (Accardo et al [1]). For the LCC calculation, the data source and calculation were conducted by using literature and a public tool (BatPaC) designed by the Argonne Institute to calculate the costs adapted to the LCC approach that will be fully developed later in the project.

Both the LCA and LCC results of the reference scenario show that the active materials associated with the active materials specially involved in the cathode are dominant in the battery pack production life cycle stage. Since MARBEL project is not focused on the chemistry of the battery, actions on this detected hotspot will not be addressed. However, important economic and environmental impacts also influence in the battery pack production stage, that are related to the housing (non-cell components). Hence, improvement on the design of this component is able to potentially decrease the environmental impacts.

This study is focused on the production phase only, and hence, it is foreseen that the environmental performance of MARBEL could improve a little bit against baseline technology. However, the main improvements in terms of environmental gains of MARBEL will be deployed during the use phase will allow better efficiency due to the technical performance. In addition, second life applications and circularity strategies at the end-of-life will be included in the LCA and LCC cradle-to-grave study, which will allow to verify decreasing of allocated impacts

The results that were obtained during the execution of Task 8.1 to which this report is linked have allowed to get the first picture for the economic and environmental performance framed in the existent battery as benchmark as inputs to the Task 8.2, Task 8.3 and WP2.

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List of abbreviations

BEV	Battery Electric Vehicle
BMS	Battery Management System
BP	Battery Packs
ADP	Abiotic Depletion Potential
ADP-FF	Abiotic Depletion Potential Fossil Fuels
AP	Acidification Potential
CE	Circular Economy
CED	Cumulative Energy Demand
EOL	End of Life
EP	Eutrophication Potential
EVs	Electric Vehicles
F-ECOTP	Fresh Water Ecotoxicity Potential
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GWP	Global Warming Potential
H-ECOTP	Human Ecotoxicity Potential
KPI	Key Project Indicators
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LCO	Lithium Cobalt Oxide
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
LIB	Lithium ion battery
LIP	Lithium Iron Phosphate
LMO	Lithium Manganese Oxide
M-ECOTP	Marine Ecotoxicity Potential
NCA	Lithium Nickel Cobalt Aluminium oxide
NMC	Nickel Manganese Cobalt
ODP	Ozone Depletion Potential
PET	Polyethylene Terephthalate
PEV	Plug-in Electric Vehicle
PHEV	Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicle
POP	Photochemical Oxidation Potential
PVDF	Polyvinyl fluoride
SoA	State of the Art
T-ECOTP	Terrestrial Water Ecotoxicity Potential
WP	Work Package

Introduction

Lithium-ion batteries (LIB onwards) are the most common source of energy in mobility applications, such as electric vehicles (EVs). EVs do not release tailpipe emissions of air pollutants such as nitrogen oxides and particulate matter, thereby are considered to be environmentally friendly modes of transport and offer significant opportunities to reduce local air pollution, GHG emissions, and traffic noise.

Economic feasibility will always be a driving force in the decision-making process when integrating EVs in city life, especially when people have low purchasing power and countries face other challenges and barriers. Therefore, an economic assessment is necessary to present an overall impression of the benefits that EVs may provide.

According to Hauschild et al. (2018) [2], the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycling Cost (LCC) in the field of mobility can be used to:

- compare different engines;
- analyse and compare different fuel types and the impact of the vehicle operation;
- compare various end-of-life scenarios and treatment options;
- identify hotspots of the analysis and main benefits and drawbacks of different vehicles;
- across three major life cycle phases (production, use, and end-of-life).

LCA and LCC are versatile techniques applicable to a range of purposes and at various stages of the product or system in order to support decision-making from the environmental and economic perspectives, respectively. In addition, LCC has been found to positively drive life cycle management by spreading the life cycle idea. Moreover, LCA and LCC are parts of a Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA). The development of the LCSA originates from the need to combine the three aspects of sustainable development (environmental, economic, and social) in a single formulation, supporting life cycle thinking [3]

MARBEL project objectives aim at designing, developing and demonstrating new modular, compact, lightweight and high-performance battery packs together with flexible and robust battery management systems for these Battery Electric Vehicle (BEV) and Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicle (PHEV), while maintaining safety levels, allowing fast, high quality and cost-effective large-scale production and following the “made by eco-design” principles. To demonstrate the improvements of MARBEL battery pack from an environmental and economic perspective, it is necessary to define a baseline scenario, constituted by a commercial LIB and estimate the environmental and economic impacts associated and compare them, later in the project, with the ones associated to MARBEL’s battery.

At this purpose, this document provides preliminary environmental and economic information about the MARBEL baseline scenario given by the Audi e-Tron 55 battery. The environmental aspects are provided by the performance of a simplified LCA of this battery while the economic aspects will be covered by the implementation of a LCA on the same battery.

The assessment of the baseline scenario will be used later on in the project, in Tasks 8.2, 8.3 and 8.4 of the project, to compare this Audi battery to the MARBEL proposed battery, from an economic and environmental point of view.

The economic and environmental assessment of the baseline scenario has been carried out using the life cycle perspective, focusing on the first two stages of the life cycle of the battery: the raw materials extraction and transformation and the production of the components of the battery and their assembling.

At this stage of the project, detailed information on the baseline battery required for a comprehensive economic and environmental assessment is not available. In order to cover this

gap, the specifications of the baseline battery have been collected using both literature, commercial and scientific sources, as it will be specified in sections 1, 2 and 3 of this document.

Section 4 of the document presents the results of this assessment that will be further used in the comparison of this baseline battery to the MARBEL battery proposal.

1. BRIEF INTRODUCTION TO LCA AND LCC METHODOLOGIES

This section presents the methodologies that will be applied for the environmental and economic assessment of the baseline scenario.

1.1 Introduction to LCA methodology

As stated in ISO 14040:2006 [4], life cycle assessment is the compilation and evaluation of potential inputs, outputs and potential environmental impacts of products, processes, or services through its life cycle. The life cycle entails the extraction raw materials, its inclusion on manufacturing processes (also called production), use, and end-of-life management (ISO 14040:2006).

The application of this methodology is ruled mainly by two international standards: ISO 14040:2006 and 14044:2006 [5]. The first one is aimed at providing a general frame for the methodology application, while ISO 14044:2006 applies different instructions in a more concrete way. Other standards (with no binding character) are focused on providing illustrative examples (ISO/TR 14047), data documentation format (ISO/TR 14048), and giving examples of goal and scope and inventory analysis (ISO14041).

The institute for environmental and sustainability (Joint Research Centre) published the International Reference Life Cycle Data System (ILCD) Handbook [6] from the abovementioned ISO rules. This consists in a series of documents aimed at adding more specificity to the ISO rules, providing consistency and quality to the LCA studies. Figure 1 provides a graphical depict of the four steps of the methodology: goal and scope definition, inventory analysis, impact assessment and interpretation. These steps rely on an iterative and holistic process in which adaptation or adjustments of any step is viable due to new findings in later steps.

Figure 1 Phases of the LCA methodology. Reproduced from ISO 14040:2006

1.1.1 Goal and scope

The goal and scope definition phase are the first step, and it represents the mainstay of the study. Since it is the basis of the study, its definition is paramount important. Since the holistic essence of LCA study, it can be modified in latter stages, but the ideal situation is to be the main starting point for the whole study. On its behalf, the scope definition describes the performance of the system. The selected function (or functions) of the system shall be reflected by the goal of the study. The scope of the study also includes a description of the limitations of the study, the allocation procedures (if needed), data requirements and its quality, the main assumptions, and the impact categories to be assessed.

The functional unit shall be coherent with the goal and the scope of the system. One of the main purpose of the functional unit is to quantify the function of the study. From its definition, the fluxes are defined based on the functional unit. After the definition of the functional unit, the reference flux is defined. The functional unit (and hence, the reference flow) must be clearly defined and be measurable.

System boundaries state what process are within the system, and its determination must be coherent with the goal of the study. The process for establish those limits must be explained. The removal of a stage from the life cycle is only allowed when no significant modifications are produced. At any case, this kind of decisions must be clearly explained and motivated.

1.1.2 Inventory analysis

In the Life Cycle Inventory analysis (LCI) data is collected in order to cover all the inputs and outputs flows within the system boundaries. As a result, LCI delivers a breakdown which entails energy and material inputs, products, wastes and emissions to atmosphere, water, and soil. The different phases are expressed according to the stated reference flow. Foreground data gives the higher data quality and ideally, is the preferred data source for filling the LCI. Nevertheless, is not always possible to complete a LCI exclusively using foreground data. In that way, different databases can be used for including predefined sets for background data associated with the upstream and downstream processes. Examples of these databases are Ecoinvent [7], and GaBi [8], which are the most implemented in the market, despite other option available.

1.1.3 Impact assessment

In the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA), the inventory is translated into potential environmental impacts. The assessments can be divided into mandatory and optional operations: In the case of mandatory elements, those are listed:

- Selection of impact categories, category indicators and models; In this step the environmental effects are listed, depending on different factors (objectives of the study, sector in which the study is focused, etc.);
- Assignment of the LCIA results (classification); Classification step uses category indicators, which matches the effects of the elements of the inventory over the selected impact categories;
- Calculation of category indicator results (characterisation); Characterisation relies on translating the matches found in classification step into potential environmental impacts. For that, characterization factors are applied, derived from the category indicators and the characterization model;
- Data quality analysis;

1.1.4 Interpretation

Interpretation has the aim to analyse results and its relation to the goal and scope definition. In this phase, following ISO 14044:2006, conclusions are reached, the limitations of the results are presented and recommendations are provided based on the findings of the preceding phases of the LCA. In this way, interpretation step allows the identification of hot spots derived from the LCI and impact assessment.

The impact assessment helps to increase the knowledge and understanding about the environmental inputs and outputs, and at the same time allows improving the inventory analysis. Following the ISO 14044:2006 guidelines “the LCIA phase shall be carefully planned to achieve the goal and scope of an LCA study. The LCIA phase shall be coordinated with other phases of the LCA to take into account the following possible omissions and sources of uncertainty”.

1.1.5 LCA indicators

The results of LCA studies can be informed through quantitative impact categories useful for the KPIs definition in the MARBEL, that, among technical objectives and perspective of developing battery solutions, will the environmental and economic circumstances linked to the proposed Battery Packs (BP) in two ways:

- By proving to be a sustainable (environmentally and ecologically) and safe alternative to a battery useable capacity against a best-in-class vehicle chosen (Audi e-Tron 55);
- By demonstrating the different improvements proposed in terms of weight reduction, extended battery life, charging time reduction, materials usage and finally, manufacturability, by an easing (dis-) assembly processes and a better assignment and avoidance of unnecessary maintenance actions;

These KPIs are listed in Table 1.

This LCA study has been carried out by EURECAT within the MARBEL project. Its basis, assumptions, and main considerations are under the guidelines of attributional Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approach described in the international standards ISO 14040:2006 and 14044:2006. This study is called to assess the manufacturing phase of a battery pack corresponding to an NMC-622 Battery pack. This battery pack is representing those installed in an Audi e-Tron, which weighs 700 kg. This technology is stated as the baseline item for the MARBEL project. Hence, the developed system within the project will be compared benchmarked against the system stated in this report.

Table 1: MARBEL’S environmental KPIs

MARBEL ENVIRONMENTAL KPIs		Unit	Description	Data required
Resource use	Abiotic depletion (elements)	kg Sb-eq	Increased extraction of resources leading to depletion of non-renewable mineral reserves	Foreground data related to main processes: Questionnaire preparation to be sent to the involved technical partners. Data such as material and energy consumption flows (input and outputs), declared emissions, by-products and products (primary data) will be demanded. Background data related
	Abiotic depletion (fossil)	MJ	Indicator of the depletion of natural fossil fuel resources	
	Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11-eq	Indicator of emissions to air that cause the destruction of the stratospheric ozone layer	
	Cumulative Energy Demand	MJ	Quantity of energy in MJ (net cal. value) per functional unit. Increased energy consumption from renewable and non-renewable energy sources	

MARBEL ENVIRONMENTAL KPIs	Unit	Description	Data required
Pollutant emissions	Acidification potential	kg SO ₂ -eq	Increased acidity of soil and water due to proton release from anthropogenic emissions
	Global Warming Potential	kg CO ₂ -eq	Increased radiative forcing due to the increase of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere
	Photochemical ozone creation potential	kg ethene-eq	Indicator of emissions of gases that affect the creation of photochemical ozone in the lower atmosphere (smog) catalysed by sunlight.
	Eutrophication potential	kg PO ₄ ³⁻ -eq	Increased biomass formation and loss of biodiversity due to release of nutrients
	Particulate matter	kg PM2.5 eq	Particulate matter formation starts with an emission of NO _x , NH ₃ , SO ₂ , or primary PM2.5 to the atmosphere, followed by atmospheric fate and chemistry in the air; NO _x , NH ₃ , and SO ₂ are transformed in air to secondary aerosols. Subsequently, PM2.5 can be inhaled by the human population, leading to an increased number of mortality cases and final damage to human health.
Toxicity risk	Human toxicity potential – Cancer	1,4-DCB-eq	Impact on humans of carcinogenic substances emitted to the environment
	Human toxicity potential – Non-Cancer	1,4-DCB-eq	Impact on humans of toxic substances emitted to the environment
	Fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity	1,4-DCB-eq	Impact on freshwater organisms of toxic substances emitted to the environment
	Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	1,4-DCB-eq/sup>	Impact on sea water organisms of toxic substances emitted to the environment
	Terrestrial ecotoxicity	1,4-DCB-eq	Impact on land organisms of toxic substances emitted to the environment
Biodiversity	Species loss potential	Sps*year	Potential loss of species due to activities performed

to upstream and downstream processes: Data that include quantities of raw material extraction for the production of products, energy sources and end-of-life scenarios (secondary data) will be extracted from Eco-Invent database.

*Data from scientific and recognised literature could be used.

1.2 Introduction to LCC methodology

LCC is as an assessment of all costs associated with the life cycle of a product. It complements environmental and social concepts during the evaluation of the sustainability of that product. The LCC methodology can be directly covered by any one or more of the actors in the product life cycle (supplier, producer, user/consumer, end-of-life-actor, thereby, this tool is useful for making good decisions and identify challenges from various perspectives, such as a product or service developer or consumer.

On the other hand, the LCC may include external costs (also called externalities) usually known as an environmental LCC, that are anticipated to be internalized in the decision-relevant future. Externalities are envisioned to include the monetized effects of environmental and social impacts not directly billed to the firm, consumer, or government, etc. that is producing, using, or handling the product. The so named “externalities” are outside the economic system, though inside the natural and social system”. In this sense, a generic assessment of the LCC can be schematically

shown as in Figure 2, where the inputs (direct costs and externalities) and outputs (revenues and externalities) occur at each stage. In MARBEL project, the externalities will be not considered due to the lack of data.

The calculation of the LCC will be done following the equations here reported.

The model for the MARBEL LCC will be detailed later in the D8.2. The model will be aligned with the LCA methodology following a cradle-to-grave approach, covering all three life cycle stages: manufacturing, operation and end-of-life. The LCC can be calculated in terms of monetary units per energy storage (€/kwh) through the Equation (1) [10].

$$LCC = \frac{MCC+CPC+OMC+EoL}{BES} \quad (1)$$

Where:

LCC: Life cycle costing of battery (Excluding the externalities), €/kWh

MCC: Cell material/component cost, €

CPC: Cell production cost, €

OMC: Operating & Maintenance, €

EoLC: End-of-life costs (Dismantling, Recycling/Reuse credits, etc.), €

BES: Battery energy storage, kWh

Please note that for the operating costs, the only cost that will be included is regarding the electricity required to charge the battery and the allocated cost of the charging device used for this purpose. There are no maintenance costs expected for sealed batteries [10].

1.2.1 LCC indicators

As part of the LCC approach, a preliminary set of indicators (Table 2) associated with the economic analysis are presented below, which are aligned with the KPIs defined in the D2.1.

Table 2 Main LCC indicators for the MARBEL project

Name	Units	Description	Data required
LCC	€/kWh	LCC as an economic indicator itself addressing the life cycle of the battery	Unit costs element/material/component/use/end-of-life
Investment cost	€/kWh	Total capital cost per unit of energy storage	Unit costs of element/material/component and cell production
Operation & Maintenance cost (O&M)	€/kWh	Total Operation & Maintenance cost	Input & output for operating cost associated with purchasing electricity required to charge the battery, and a charging device may need to be purchased. Data related replacement operations
Disposal and recycling/reuse costs	€/kWh	Cost associated with disposal (landfill, incineration treatments) and/or recycling of materials and components and reuse of battery	Flow allocation between different materials in an end-of-life (regional/European) scenario
Savings from recyclability	€/kWh	Only savings directly related to material recycling	Material recycling credits
Payback Time of MARBEL batteries	Years	Calculation of the time needed for the payback of the extra initial costs	Cash flows of the system Interest rate
Electricity pricing	€/kWh	Cost of electricity acquisition having into account time horizon	Peak & Off-Peak electricity prices (Energy operators and official statistics). European average price of electricity at consumer to be considered.
LCC	€/kWh	LCC as an economic indicator itself addressing the life cycle of the battery	Unit costs element/material/component/use/end-of-life
Investment cost	€/kWh	Total capital cost per unit of energy storage	Unit costs of element/material/component and cell production

These costs consider, in most of the cases, the assessment of the first lifecycle stage, that is the cost of the materials employed in the production of the battery. This assessment is mainly conditioned by the cost of extraction and conditioning of materials such as lithium, cobalt, nickel and copper, that are subject to market variations that consider their risk of supply and their scarcity. In addition, the MARBEL objectives to reduce the weight of the battery pack, materials related to the housing, electric distribution, modules, communications and thermal management, will be also considered.

Another aspect to be considered is the use phase of the battery, that includes both the costs related to the charging operations (cost of the electricity) and potential operation and maintenance

costs. The first one will depend on the cost of the electricity, though some assumptions can be done to establish an average cost per kWh.

Furthermore, the costs associated to the end-of-life (removing from the vehicle and recycling operations) shall be added. Costs of the repurposing of the battery for a potential second life can be left out the boundaries of the assessment, to be included in the LCC of a battery second life stage.

At this stage of the project, the KPIs listed above will not be assessed in this deliverable for the baseline scenario, due to the lack of information.

2. LiB ECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL STATE OF THE ART

This section includes a short compilation of the main literature sources that have been used in the assessment of the baseline scenario.

2.1 SoA of environmental aspects related to LiB

2.1.1. Introduction

LiB have been used in many places since 1990s as components to store both power and energy in consumer electronics and portable devices [11]. Due to LiB features and functional aspects such as its high energy density, long cycle life and high energy efficiency, LiB become useful for its use in BEVs [12]. Although batteries based on lead-acid, nickel-metal hydride and sodium-nickel-chloride have been used for BEVs in the past, LiB have been emerged as the dominant technology in the recent years because of the advantageous characteristics of lithium [1], [13], [14]. The main advantage of this metal is the performance on electrochemical potential, giving higher power and energy density than previous battery chemistries [15]. This latter is what makes LiBs predominate over the rest of the batteries for having higher potential for energy storage as it has been above mentioned.

The main components of the LiB are the electrolyte, the separator, the cathode, and the anode [16]. The anode is usually composed of graphite and a Polyvinyl Fluoride (PVDF) binder [17]. In the case of the cathode, different chemistries of this component have been widely studied in the last years. Lithium Cobalt Oxide (LCO) and Lithium Manganese Oxide (LMO) cathodes were the batteries used in the first serial-production of electric vehicles [1]. However, the focus was put into other chemistries like Nickel Manganese Cobalt oxide (NMC), Lithium Iron Phosphate (LIP) and, more recently, Lithium Nickel Cobalt Aluminium oxide (NCA) [14], [18]. Among these batteries, NCA batteries present the highest energy density followed by NMC batteries. Considering that NCA batteries result in less safety, NMC batteries are currently the choice for many electric powertrains [1], [14], [19]. In this sense, the investigation and innovation activities have been focused on NMC batteries [14], [20]. The typical cathode combination in NMC batteries is one-third Nickel, one-third Manganese, and one-third Cobalt. Nevertheless, due to the high economic cost of Cobalt and its limited supply, battery manufacturers are replacing the cobalt content by nickel [14], [21]–[24]. From the technical point of view, the energy density of the Nickel-based cell is higher than Cobalt-based cells and, despite Cobalt-based cells have higher voltage, Nickel-based cells have longer cycle life [14], [25], [26]. Different combinations have been proved; however, successful results are obtained with NMC532 (with 5 parts of Nickel, 3 parts of Manganese, and 2 parts of Cobalt), NMC-622 (with 6 parts of Nickel, 2 parts of Manganese, and 2 parts of Cobalt) and NMC811 (with 8 parts of Nickel, 1 part of Manganese, and 1 part of Cobalt). The current collectors at the cathode are made of aluminium foils whereas in the anode are made of copper foils [1].

In the LCA studies, the authors classify the entire life cycle of the product (Figure 3) in different stages including from the extraction of raw materials, through production, use and recycling, up to the disposal of remaining waste. In particular, the environmental performance of the extraction of raw materials stage considers the potential environmental impacts associated to the component production or the resource extraction prior to the battery production. In the production stage, the impacts are more associated to the battery manufacture which includes the production of battery components such as the cathode, the battery cell, and the production of the non-cell materials [1]. The use phase is related to impacts mainly caused by the amount of electricity lost during the recharging phase over the whole life of the battery whereas the end-of-life stage include the impact of the recycling process, the savings obtained due to the replacing of raw materials by recycled ones as well as the impacts needed to complete the disposal of non-recycled materials.

Figure 3 System boundary of the LCA of the Li-ion batteries [27]

All of the reported studies performed the impact assessment through different categories, which are usually the following: Abiotic Resource Depletion Potential (ADP), Abiotic Resource Potential of Fossil Fuels (ADP-FF), Global Warming Potential (GWP), Greenhouse Gas Emissions (GHG), Acidification Potential (AP), Eutrophication Potential (EP), Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP) Photochemical Oxidation Potential (POP), Human Toxicity Potential (HTP), Freshwater Aquatic Ecotoxicity Potential (F-ECOTP), Marine a*Aquatic Ecotoxicity potential (M-ECOTP), Terrestrial Ecotoxicity Potential (T-ECOTP) and Cumulative Energy Demand (CED).

In the case of the NMC batteries, many studies have assessed the impacts in the production stage but not in the other life cycle stages. In fact, it is usual that LCA of NMC batteries do not include the end-of-life and use stages, so these stages are only evaluated in few studies [19] [1]. In addition, despite the several LCA studies of LIB, the performed assessments present significant differences, producing uncertainty in the results which makes it difficult to provide correct direction to reduce environmental impacts of this kind of batteries [19].

2.1.2. Reported results in life cycle assessment of LIBs

2.1.2.1. Production

According to many authors, the production phase generates the highest environmental impact [1], [12], [27]–[30] considering it as the most environmentally sensitive phase in the LCA of LIB. Nevertheless, the emissions reported significantly varies between studies due to the differences

on the data of the energy demand in cell manufacture and battery pack assembly, causing significant variations in the impact assessment results as shown in Figure 4 [19]. In fact, Hall et al. [31] observed from the reported studies that between 56 and 494 kg CO₂/kWh are associated to the battery production. This occurs since battery industries usually patent their information, limiting the provided primary data and thus the authors are forced to use secondary energy data from industry reports or even make their own estimations [19].

Figure 4 GHG emissions of battery production in reported studied [19]

Among the battery pack production, cell manufacturing accounts 45% of GHG emissions, making it the key contributor, whereas 19% of the GHG emissions are stemmed from the production and manufacture of materials and components for batteries (cathode, anode, current collectors, electrolyte, separator, and pouch materials). Considering that the production of non-cell materials to battery production accounts between 36 and 46% for many impact categories (ADP, CED, ADP-FF, and GWP) taking to account both cell materials and non-cell materials are important when assessing the environmental sustainability [1]. Cell materials include active cathode material, graphite, binder, copper, aluminium, electrolyte, and plastics, whereas non-cell materials include copper, aluminium, steel, Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET), and electronics.

In addition of the impact caused by the metals extraction for cathode production, electronic components are also significant during the production phase since they represent 71% of the eutrophication impact and 58% of photochemical smog impacts [28].

2.1.2.2. Use phase

Manufacturers of EV specify that when LIB loss around 20 and 30% of its initial energy or density power they have to be removed given that it is not useful in a vehicle [32]. The energy conversions losses, the energy required to carry the weight of the battery and the carbon intensity of the electricity produce indirect emissions of the battery during its use. In the case of the energy conversion losses, they depend on the energy efficiency of the battery as well as on the operational energy demand of the vehicle. For this reason, determining the correct energy efficiency of the battery is an important aspect. Nevertheless, this is difficult to determine since no available information could be found regarding energy efficiency of LIB. Thus, LCA studies have usually not considered the variation on the efficiencies due to the differences on the cell

format types or the differences on the cathode material. In this sense, efficiencies contemplated in LCA studies of LIB vary from 85% to 90% [28], [33] or 95% [17]), which directly influences on the LCA impact results. According to Zackrisson et al. [28]) the internal battery efficiency has an important relation with the impact on the use phase emissions since the higher the internal efficiency, the lower impact of use phase. Regarding GWP, the use phase accounts almost 10% of the emissions due to battery losses, which represents 25 kg CO₂ eq/kWh [1].

2.1.2.3. End-of-life

The end-of-life of batteries is reached when LIB must be retired from EVs. Including this stage in the LCA could benefit the total battery impact in the range of 3 to 25% [1]. Metal recovery during the end-of-life phase can potentially avoid 10-30% of the environmental impact from battery production. However, the environmental impacts vary depending on the modelling approach of end-of-life selected (Figure 5) [11]. The first step in end-of-life is waste collection and the high collection rate is important to perform an effective recycling. As a previous step, collected batteries are usually pre-treated which often includes dismantling, sorting and shredding for metals recovery [34]. The chemical metal extraction can be performed through pyro metallurgy which involves high temperatures or hydrometallurgy and the use of aggressive acids. The use of recycled metals in the production stage using pyro metallurgical methods can reduce primary energy consumption by 5-56%, and GHG emissions by 23%. In the case of hydrometallurgical methods, the benefits can increase since they required less electrical energy and produces less air pollution, but this method has an important disadvantage due to the high amount of water consumption. In general, the main environmental effects in the recycling process are the landfill of the waste material, the energy consumption and the plastics incineration, among others. Hence, the main environmental effect on global warming of pyro metallurgy is the incineration of plastics whereas in the case of hydrometallurgy is landfill. For the average end-of-life treatment options, a reduction on the emissions in the range of 16-32 kg CO₂ eq/kWh has been reported [35]. Considering the important environmental impact caused by the cathode production, the use of recycled cathodes, aluminium and copper in LIB production might reduce the GHG emissions by 54% compared to their production with virgin metals [18]. Nevertheless, although reported studies affirm that high rates of metals can be recovered by recycling methodologies, low recycling rates are in current practice [36], [37].

Figure 5 Representation of the environmental impact variations depending on the end-of-life modelling approach selected [11]

Based on the state of the art performed above, the main remarks are highlighted as follows.

- The production phase is the main contributor to the total environmental impact in life cycle of batteries, followed by the use phase and the end-of-life phase;
- Battery cell production is one of the key contributors in the life cycle GHG emissions;
- Optimizing the materials used in the production process that have higher environmental burden and the improving of the utilization of the materials used such as lithium, manganese, cobalt or aluminium, will reduce the environmental impact of battery production process;
- The improvement in the technologies currently available will involve an improvement in the performance of an important part of environmental impact categories;
- The energy is also a key contributor in the total environmental impact, so the use of renewable energy sources in the production phase as well as in the rest of the stages may also result in a benefit in the life cycle assessment of batteries;
- There are few studies including both the use phase and the end-of-life phase in their LCA due to the difficult accessibility of data collection from battery industry and recyclers. Hence, efforts are needed to overcome this limitation, increasing the quality and the confidence of the data as well as of the reported results;

These remarks and the results obtained after the environmental and economic analysis performed in this report, the most suitable eco-design strategies were compiled in the deliverable 2.5.

2.2 SoA of economic aspects related to LiB

There are a large number of references in literature that assess the costs and economic impacts of LIB for EVs. The authors of this deliverable have selected some of them considering their completeness, the inference to the project objectives and their date of publication.

The BP of EVs can represent between the 35-50% of the total costs of the vehicle, such as shown in **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia..**

Figure 6 EVs component cost distribution [38]

This range is mainly due to a high observable variation in battery costs, since economies of scale can be triggered depending on the total number of vehicles produced. Therefore, battery costs can vary depending on the number of units produced [39]. **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** shows an overview of battery costs of battery packs of different vehicle brands, where the generic Audi e-Tron is also listed with a cost of 157 €/kWh [40].

Table 3 Battery pack cost evolution

Vehicle	Model year	Assumed Units per year	Pack Costs
BMW i3	2014	15000	396 €/kWh
GM Bolt	2016	20000	224 €/kWh
BMW i3	2017	25000	254 €/kWh
Renault Zoe	2017	40000	208 €/kWh
Tesla Model 3	2018	100000	164 €/kWh
Audi 3-Tron	2019	100000	157 €/kWh

Table 3 shows the evolution of LIB packs worldwide between 2011 and 2030 where it can be observed that the cost of the LIB packs has decreased over the years. The deployment of the electric vehicle fleet, the expected large volume of LIB pack production and the technology development are the major drivers to the production cost decrease.

In this light, an analysis of costs considering the life cycle perspective is useful to detect the parameters or hotspots that allows to reduce the impacts to achieve more sustainable batteries from an economic point of view.

According to Gaines et al [41], the total life-cycle cost of a battery is the sum of its production cost, costs accrued during its useful life, and any cost or credit from recycling. For Li-ion batteries, the production costs dominate, and the material costs are the largest contributor.

Figure 7 LIB pack costs worldwide between 2011 and 2030 [42]

Table 4 Costs for traction battery packs and battery cells today until 2030 [39]

Cell specs		Vehicle type	2017	2020	Potential (2030)	Unit	
Battery cells	Large cell (60Ah)		92	86	76	€/kWh	
	Small cell (4,5 Ah)		110	103	92	€/kWh	
Ratio battery pack costs to cell costs (1)			1,35	1,3	1,25		
Battery pack	Large cell (60Ah)		124	112	95	€/kWh	
	Small cell (4,5 Ah)		BEV (2)	148	130	115	€/kWh
	Large cell		PHEV (3)	176	165	141	€/kWh
	Ratio PHEV to BEV battery pack costs (3)			1,42	1,47	1,48	
Additional fixed costs per battery pack (4)					200	€	

(1) The ratio takes into consideration cost for cell contacting technology, battery cooling, slave BMSs (one slave for 10-12 battery cell connected in series) etc.

(2) BEVs with a battery capacity of 60 to 90kWh.

(3) PHEVs with a battery capacity of 5 to 10 kWh.

(4) The fixed battery costs have to be added on top of the battery pack costs, which can be calculated using the EUR/kWh values. In particular, these costs should be taken into consideration for smaller battery packs where the fixed cost components are responsible for a larger part of the battery pack costs. Fixed and partly fixed cost components of battery packs include contactors, fuses, insulation monitoring unit, BMS master unit, plugs and battery housing (depends on battery design and mounting inside the vehicle)

Going down to a cost breakdown of the BP, Table 4 provides a review of the values for fixed battery costs (which are independent from the battery size), as well as a ratio which gives an approximate relationship between battery cell costs and the BP costs [38].

Cells represent about 70% of total battery pack costs, thereby cell production is the most important step of battery production to target in order to reduce the price of battery packs. In this sense, Figure 8, Figure 9 and Figure 10 highlight each step's cost share, major challenges, and most cost-intensive processes associated with the cell production process. The analysis is based on the assumption that prismatic cells are the dominant design used in EVs battery packs [43]. Understanding the three major steps of the cells production allows to identify how future production processes can reduce the cost of manufacturing battery cells.

EXHIBIT 4 | The Battery Cell Production Process

ELECTRODE PRODUCTION: 39% of battery cell production costs

Figure 8 The battery cell production process [43]

CELL ASSEMBLY: 20% of battery cell production costs

Figure 9 The cell assembly cost breakdown [43]

CELL FINISHING: 41% of battery cell production costs

Source: BCG analysis.

Figure 10 The cell finishing costs [43]

3. DESCRIPTION OF THE BASELINE SCENARIO

MARBEL BP will be compared with the 95kWh (around 84 kWh useable) Audi e-Tron 55 BP that will be considered as the baseline scenario. The total weight of the battery pack is around 700 kg (including the battery pack itself, the housing and the control modules). A description of the main characteristics of the Audi e-Tron 55 battery are presented in D2.1 [44] and are summarized in Figure 11 and the Audi e-Tron layout and e-Tron battery prototype are shown in Figure 12.

Audi e-Tron 55 Specifications (95 kWh BP, around 84kWh useable)					
Range (Real)	Cold Weather	Mild Weather	Energy Consumption	Cold Weather	Mild Weather
City	350 km	495 km	City	239 Wh/km	169 Wh/km
Highway	255 km	315 km	Highway	328 Wh/km	265 Wh/km
Combined	300 km	395 km	Combined	279 Wh/km	212 Wh/km

Figure 11 Audi e-Tron 55 Battery specifications

The battery in the Audi e-Tron 55 quattro is a lithium-ion battery with a total capacity of 95 kWh, of which approximately 88 percent (around 83.6 kWh) is used, although Audi has extended the utilization range to 91 percent (86.5 kWh) since the end of November 2019 [45]. The main characteristics of the battery can be summarized as follows:

- Total battery capacity: 95 kWh;
- Usable battery capacity: 86,5 kWh (91 %);
- Battery weight: 700 kg;
- Battery energy density: 136 Wh/kg;
- Cells: 432 (108s4p);
- Chemistry: NCM 622;
- Manufacturer: LG Chem;
- TMS: active liquid cooling;
- Dimensions: 2,28 long, 1,63 wide and 0,34 high;
- Charging power output: 150 kW;

Figure 12 Audi e-Tron layout and e-Tron battery prototype [46], [47]

The characteristics of the Audi e-Tron 55 battery are used to be introduced in BatPaC excel spreadsheet (Section 4.2) in order to simulate the further details regarding its architecture and composition, that will support the LCC to have an estimation of the costs associated to the production of this battery.

As it has been indicated, at this stage of the project, a cradle-to-gate approach is considered for the assessment of the baseline scenario battery. Therefore, results that will be calculated will focus on the cost of the materials and the production process of the battery. That will cover the first two items in equation 1:

- MCC: Cell material/Component cost, €
- CPC: Cell production cost, €

4. LCA AND LCC OF THE BASELINE SCENARIO

LCA of the baseline scenario Include the inventory data used in the baseline scenario as per the paper and supporting materials

4.1 LCA of the baseline scenario

4.1.1 Goal and scope for the LCA calculation

The main aim of this study is to determine the environmental performance of an NMC-622 battery placed in an Audi e-Tron. In this sense, the expected outputs are the hotspots of the reference technology. Further in the project, these hotspots will be the base to contribute to the design parameters of the MARBEL battery.

Hence, this report explores the environmental impact of the baseline scenario of MARBEL project. Coupled to that, it is intended that this report will be a preliminary framework for the comparison against the MARBEL technologies which are currently in the market.

This report itself does not contains product comparisons entailing registered brands. Nevertheless, during MARBEL project, this kind of comparisons will be deployed in order to determine the potential environmental gains of MARBEL technology. Because of that, a critical review could be required with the aim of avoiding bias and commercial conflicts.

The present study is called to determine the environmental performance of the baseline scenario for future MARBEL assessments. Therefore, the functional unit is determined as “the production phase of an NMC-622 BP placed in an Audi e-Tron”. Since during further development of the project different phases will be added (use phase, end-of-life), the mentioned functional unit will be modified in order to give the appropriate outputs required for final results.

Regarding the scenario description, this system is based in a single scenario scheme. In this line, it is foreseen during the project to update the scenario scheme in order to cover all the situations required by the project. In reference to allocation procedures, no allocation rules are applied since no by-products are listed during the inventory. Nevertheless, future updates of the study could consider allocation rules due to potential multifunctionality of the system.

System boundaries are focused on production phase of the NMC-622 battery. In this line, the main inputs are considered: energy, chemical reagents and capital goods for the production steps. Since the study is not focused at this point in use nor end-of-life, the system is considered as a cradle-to-gate distribution. This scope is selected because of the availability of data from literature to describe this battery, being more focused on the production stage. Nevertheless, updates of the system will be included when MARBEL developments are advanced in the project, both use and end-of-life stages will be included. Then, the distribution of the system will be based on a cradle-to-grave LCA where recycling and second life application at the life cycle study will give a circular approach to the whole system

4.1.2 Inventory data for the LCA

As stated above, this study considers the production of the different parts of an NMC-622 battery, which is used on an Audi e-Tron. This battery pack in particular weighs 700 kg in this car model.

Information contained in the inventory of this study is based on literature, mainly in the information published by Accardo et al.[1]. In this line, the source of information contained in the present study is like the one recommended from the ISO 14040:44, this is, from scientific literature and recognised databases.

The study system is divided into different steps, according to the parts of the battery pack: Cell materials (containing chemicals from the cells, including cathode) and non-cell parts (containing external aluminium case, wiring, and electronics for BMS). The information of the inventory is shown in Table 5 **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia..** As stated in the goal and scope chapter, the functional unit of the study is the production of one NMC-622 battery pack placed in an Audi e-Tron. Hence, the inventory shown in **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** is scaled for a 700kg battery pack. In the same way, results will be referenced to this unit.

Table 5 Inventory for a NMC-622 battery pack, placed in an Audi e-Tron, weighted at 700kg [1]

Category classification	Item	Units	Battery pack
General breakdown	Active cathode material	kg	176.17
	Cell materials (excluding cathode)	kg	367.75
	Active non-cell materials	kg	156.08
	Total battery pack weigh	kg	700.00
Cathode materials	Chemical factory (organics)	kg	7.05E-08
	Cobalt sulphate	kg	94.43
	Nickel sulphate	kg	94.25
	Lithium carbonate	kg	67.47
	Manganese sulphate	kg	91.96
	Sodium hydroxide	kg	148.69
	Ammonium hydroxide	kg	20.61
	Natural gas	MJ	7504.94
	Electricity	MJ	4439.54
	Water	kg	1338.91
Cell materials	Chemical factory, organics	amount	1.47E-07
	Aluminium	kg	34.94
	Graphite	kg	81.27
	PVC	kg	12.50
	Heat	MJ	8678.93
	Electricity	kwh	514.85
	EC	kg	25.37
	PP	kg	5.88
	LiPF ₆	kg	9.19
	PE	kg	1.47
	PET	kg	1.10
	Copper	kg	67.67

	DC	kg	25.37
	Carbon black	kg	9.93
	NMP	kg	1.10
Non-cell materials	Metal factory	amount	7.18E-08
	Copper	kg	0.47
	Aluminium	kg	28.72
	Steel	kg	1.09
	PET	kg	0.78
	Electronics	amount	0.62
	Energy from assembly	Electricity	kWh
Heat, natural gas		MJ	5460.00

4.1.3 Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA)

In this section the quantification and evaluation of environmental impacts associated to the NMC-622 BP will be summarised based on the LCA built using SimaPro software, v.9.0.

In accordance with ISO 14044:2006 standard, one of the mandatory elements on every life cycle assessment is “the selection of impact categories, category indicators and characterization models”. Therefore, it is essential a selection of the impact assessment method to be used.

In this study, different characterization methods have been used at the same time; the main impact assessment method selected is the CML-IA (baseline, version 4.7). It is a LCIA methodology developed by the Centre of Environmental Science (CML) of Leiden University in The Netherlands. For the purpose of the study, the problem-oriented approach is the most reasonable way to determine impact. To complement this selection, Cumulative Energy Demand has been also included Table 6 **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** shows the selected impact categories.

Table 6 Selected impact categories considered in the study

Impact category	Units
Abiotic depletion (elements)	kg Sb eq
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	MJ
Global warming (GWP100a)	kg CO ₂ eq
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq
Fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq
Photochemical oxidation	kg C ₂ H ₄ eq
Acidification	kg SO ₂ eq
Eutrophication	kg PO ₄ --- eq
Cumulative energy demand	GJ

Following the distribution of components already stated in the inventory analysis chapter, the results will show the environmental performance from the general approach to each main part (cell material, cathode and non-cell materials). First of all, Figure 13 shows the impact percentage distribution of the whole battery pack, and Table 7 **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** shows the obtained numerical results.

Figure 13 Percentage distribution of environmental impact in the categories analysed for the production of a 700kg NMC-622 battery pack installed in an Audi e-Tron

Table 7 Environmental impact results in the categories analysed for the production of a 700 kg NMC-622 battery pack installed in an Audi e-Tron

Impact category	Unit	Total	1.1. Cell materials	1.2. Non-cell materials	1.3. Assembly energy
Abiotic depletion (elements)	kg Sb eq	4.04	3.93	0.10	0.01
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	MJ	128564.31	79367.47	4543.10	44653.75
Global warming (GWP100a)	kg CO ₂ eq	12542.13	7248.33	458.80	4835.00
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	6.00E-04	5.19E-04	2.41E-05	5.76E-05
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	28766.76	26236.87	825.85	1704.05
Fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	34286.93	32312.17	665.47	1309.29
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	tn1,4-DB eq	52300.96	43338.63	1664.14	7298.18
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	40.21	31.06	1.41	7.74
Photochemical oxidation	kg C ₂ H ₄ eq	12.81	11.83	0.19	0.79
Acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	319.57	295.88	2.90	20.79
Eutrophication	kg PO ₄ --- eq	24.61	19.17	0.87	4.57
Cumulative energy demand	GJ	158.48	99.73	5.90	52.84

Results shown in both Figure 13 and **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** point to different clear trends. By one hand, the main contributions come from the cell materials, reaching in some categories, such as the abiotic depletion, almost 100% of the contribution. By other hand, assembly energy is also one of the most contributing stages, reaching values close to 40% of the impact in different categories. Lastly, the contribution of non-cell materials can be considered as residual, due to the highest contributions are stated on 5% of the total impacts. From these results, different assessments will be deployed: First of all, the study of cell materials due to the great contribution that it shows. Coupled to that, non-cell materials will be also studied, due to, despite the low contribution, to determine the sources of its impacts.

In this regard, Figure 14 and Table 8 **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** show the obtained results for cell materials, in terms of percentage distribution and absolute values, respectively.

Figure 14 Percentage distribution of environmental impact by materials for the production of an NMC-622 cell of a 700kg battery pack installed in an Audi e-Tron

Table 8 Environmental impact results by materials for the production of an NMC-622 cell of a 700kg battery pack installed in an Audi e-Tron

Impact category	Units	Total	Chemical factory	Aluminium, primary, ingot	Graphite	Polyvinyl chloride, suspension	Heat	Electricity	Ethylene carbonate	Polypropylene	Lithium hexafluorophosphate	Polyethylene, low density	Polyethylene terephthalate	Copper	Dimethyl carbonate	Carbon black	N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone	Cathode
Abiotic depletion (elements)	kg Sb eq	0.01	8.86E-03	2.74 E-03	1.00 E-04	1.12E-03	3.14 E-04	1.15 E-03	1.44E-03	2.06 E-03	0.01	5.29E-05	0.12	0.12	2.09E-03	2.96E-4	1.57E-04	3.61
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	MJ	327.51	10324.92	101.60	930.65	8343.00	6879.34	1252.81	633.41	2761.69	157.97	110.85	1714.03	1776.43	1112.76	158.82	39363.45	327.51
Global warming (GWP100a)	kg CO2 eq	31.60	1192.94	8.36	45.01	523.20	771.94	58.13	19.69	250.89	5.35	5.07	166.66	80.97	27.25	10.22	3738.87	31.60
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq		2.07E-06	2.86 E-05	9.17 E-07	2.16 E-05	5.70E E-05	5.59 E-06	2.26 E-06	3.99 E-07	3.25E-05	1.33E-07	2.57 E-07	1.51 E-05	5.82 E-06	1.42E-05	9.53E-06	3.09E-04
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	372.06	677.17	4.93	46.38	45.85	281.93	214.38	9.06	613.59	2.63	4.34	10764.86	234.60	12.72	8.72	11813.69	372.06
Fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	212.92	760.24	3.14	29.70	22.96	217.49	39.22	6.27	202.03	1.88	2.43	6760.35	58.46	7.03	5.87	22590.52	212.92
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	tn1,4-DB eq	279.00	3157.87	8.26	59.24	45.84	1218.160	70.142	12.97	4662.66	4.43	4.98	7765.32	106.0	11.37	13.43	24052.08	279.00
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	0.29	2.01	0.02	0.09	0.11	1.29	0.09	0.02	0.79	0.01	0.01	3.81	0.14	0.02	0.02	21.02	0.29
Photochemical oxidation	kg C2H4 eq	11.32	0.02	0.38	2.12E-03	0.01	0.05	0.13	0.02	4.02 E-03	0.13	3.08 E-03	1.17 E-03	0.22	0.07	0.01	0.00	10.28
Acidification	kg SO2 eq	0.33	6.66	0.05	0.18	0.59	3.44	0.21	0.07	2.34	0.02	0.02	6.15	0.31	0.16	0.05	262.56	0.33
Eutrophication	kg PO4--- eq	0.16	1.33	0.01	0.06	0.09	0.76	0.07	0.02	0.48	0.01	0.01	3.48	0.11	0.02	0.02	11.72	0.16
Cumulative energy demand	GJ	95.44	0.50	11.47	0.12	1.10	9.30	8.18	1.51	0.71	3.76	0.18	0.12	3.06	2.14	1.19	0.19	51.84

From the obtained results, the most striking aspect is the contribution coming from cathode production. In particular, this component implies at least half of the impact of every category. Even in some of them, like abiotic depletion elements, the major part of it (almost 95%) comes from the production of the cathode.

Apart from the cathode, which is considered as a component, the rest of the impact results could be classified as the following: minerals and raw materials, energy, chemical reagents, and other materials. After the cathode, minerals and raw materials are the most contributing aspect, mainly because of the raw materials extraction and manufacturing: Copper stands out on categories related to toxicity, while aluminium is placed on a 10% average. On its behalf, energy consumption during the production (divided into heat and electricity) has relatively important contributions in some categories. The most affected are abiotic depletion (fossil fuels), global warming and cumulative energy demand, having 20% of contribution on average in those categories. In relation to chemical reagents, the most affecting item is lithium hexafluorosulphate, but it is still not very representative. The most involved category is marine ecotoxicity, where the contribution is close to 10%. Regarding other inputs, like plastics and other materials, the contribution is negligible.

Since the contribution of the cathode production is the most important during the cell materials, and hence, over the battery pack, it will be assessed in the same way than the previous assessments. In this way, Figure 15 and Table 9 **Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** show the obtained results for the hotspot analysis.

Figure 15 Environmental impact percentage distribution for the production of an NMC-622 cathode of a 700kg battery pack installed in an Audi e-Tron

Table 9 Environmental impact results for the production of an NMC-622 cathode of a 700kg battery pack installed in an Audi e-Tron

Impact category	Unit	Total	Chemical factory	Cobalt	Nickel	Lithium carbonate	Manganese	Sodium hydroxide	Ammonia	Heat	Electricity	Water, deionised
Abiotic depletion elements	kg Sb eq	3.76	2.43 E-03	3.60	0.13	0.01	0.01	5.09 E-03	4.10 E-03	3.23 E-04	1.44 E-03	8.21 E-03
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	MJ	41000.46	89.72	9564.83	11214.26	1426.18	2763.66	1779.23	606.80	4125.45	9425.38	4.97
Global warming (GWP100a)	kg CO2 eq	3894.35	8.66	909.53	1083.00	124.65	252.82	164.23	35.85	258.71	1056.47	0.43
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	3.22E-04	5.68 E-07	7.30 E-05	7.77 E-05	1.08 E-05	1.65 E-05	1.02 E-04	5.00 E-06	2.82 E-05	7.55 E-06	2.31 E-07
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	12304.99	101.92	1744.29	9097.71	193.68	557.95	176.38	23.19	22.67	386.61	0.59
Fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	23529.99	58.33	1357.89	19883.08	123.96	1661.55	125.06	10.11	11.35	298.25	0.41
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	tn1,4-DB eq	25052.33	76.43	3194.39	17806.43	220.90	1735.50	308.61	17.99	22.66	1668.61	0.76
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	21.89	0.08	4.17	14.40	0.28	0.56	0.56	0.04	0.05	1.75	1.38E-03
Photochemical oxidation	kg C2H4 eq	10.70	4.34E-03	0.22	10.16	0.03	0.05	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.18	1.45E-4
Acidification	kg SO2 eq	273.48	0.09	8.47	256.54	0.91	1.53	0.81	0.13	0.29	4.71	3.23E-03
Eutrophication	kg PO4--- eq	12.21	0.04	2.93	6.47	0.59	0.73	0.34	0.02	0.04	1.04	7.39E-04
Cumulative Energy Demand	GJ	53.99	0.13	12.82	15.74	1.78	4.50	2.50	0.67	4.60	11.20	0.06

From the above results, it is clearly seen that the main contributions come from the extraction and manufacturing of the cathode active materials, cobalt and nickel. In the case of cobalt, the main impacts are related to abiotic depletion elements (95%), due to their extraction in mining activities. The contribution of cobalt is present in almost all the categories with variable contributions, having its maximum at 25%. In relation to nickel, it is the main contributor of the system, affecting especially to toxicity categories, as well as photochemical oxidation and acidification. Apart of these categories, nickel abatement and manufacturing has similar contribution than cobalt in the rest of categories (20-40%), with the exception of abiotic depletion. Energy consumption is the other main contributor of the system: especially on abiotic depletion, global warming, ozone layer depletion and cumulative energy demand. During all of these categories, the impacts coming from heat and electricity production is near of 40%.

The last assessment is focused on the non-cell materials. This aspect covers those parts of the battery which are not directly related with the chemistry of the battery: housing, BMS and wiring, mainly. As previous assessments, Figure 16 and Table 10 show the obtained results.

Figure 16 Percentage distribution of environmental impact for the production of an NMC-622 non-cell materials of a 700kg battery pack installed in an Audi e-Tron

Table 10 Environmental impact results for the production of an NMC-622 non-cell materials of a 700kg battery pack installed in an Audi e-Tron

Impact category	Units	Total	Metal working factory	Copper	Wire drawing, copper	Aluminium, wrought alloy	Sheet rolling, aluminium	Steel, low-alloyed, hot rolled	Sheet rolling, steel	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, amorphous	Injection moulding	Power supply unit
Abiotic depletion	kg Sb eq	0.09	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.07	1.09E-03	4.26 E-05	4.29 E-06	4.74 E-05	7.86 E-06	0.01
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels)	MJ	4347.28	115.91	46.15	4.10	3615.26	201.08	19.86	4.32	53.01	13.64	273.95
Global warming (GWP100a)	kg CO2 eq	439.03	8.98	3.72	0.35	378.15	17.98	2.20	0.43	2.43	1.00	23.79
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	2.31 E-05	1.05 E-06	3.98 E-07	4.99 E-08	1.77 E-05	9.56 E-07	1.13 E-07	2.46 E-08	1.23 E-07	9.25 E-08	2.05 E-06
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	790.25	7.84	327.82	13.10	284.71	8.99	10.78	0.21	2.08	0.49	134.23
Fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	636.79	5.33	196.63	7.99	316.66	9.98	5.11	0.46	1.16	0.42	93.03
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	tn1,4-DB eq	1592.41	12.47	225.65	9.81	1159.86	37.11	6.46	0.61	2.38	1.39	136.63
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.35	0.03	0.16	0.01	0.92	0.04	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14
Photochemical oxidation	kg C2H4 eq	0.18	3.04 E-03	0.01	4.07 E-04	0.14	3.95 E-03	9.76 E-04	1.46 E-04	5.59 E-04	2.55 E-04	0.02
Acidification	kg SO2 eq	2.77	0.06	0.24	0.01	2.18	0.08	0.01	1.62 E-03	0.01	4.09 E-03	0.18
Eutrophication	kg PO4--- eq	0.84	0.02	0.10	4.37 E-03	0.58	0.03	0.01	7.16 E-04	2.58 E-03	1.83 E-03	0.09
Cumulative Energy Demand	GJ	5.64	0.15	0.08	0.06	4.64	0.26	0.02	0.05	0.06	0.01	0.37

In the same way than the previous assessments, different trends can be extracted from the presented results. First of all, aluminium production has the main contribution of the system having its minimum near to 40% of human toxicity. Other contributions have also constant impacts over the categories, but in a residual way: BMS (considered with a proxy from Ecoinvent) contributes with 10% of the impacts on average. On its behalf, copper also has important effects toxicity categories, especially in human ecotoxicity. This trend is also present in cell materials assessment, in which copper contributions are focused on these categories.

4.2 LCC of the baseline scenario

4.2.1 Goal and scope for the LCC calculation

Aligned with the LCA approach, the scope of the LCC assessment for the baseline scenario will be “from cradle to gate”, that is to say, the life cycle stages including the raw materials extraction, the production of the components and the production of the battery (assembly of cells and battery pack). The remaining life cycle stages (use and end-of-life) will be fully addressed in D8.2 and included later on in the project.

The LCC assessment of the baseline scenario will be carried out considering two main sources of data. On the one hand, data coming from Audi and battery manufacture datasheet regarding the e-Tron battery and data from literature (scientific articles). On the other hand, the Battery Performance and Cost model (BatPaC)[48] , developed by the Argonne Institute, that will be used to characterize economically the baseline battery.

It is worth noting that since the scope of the BatPaC model, partial recycling end-of-life costs are considered in the LCC study, which are associated with materials rejection and recycling allocated at the beginning of the life cycle stage. On the contrary, costs related to the battery disassembly and recycling process are not considered, such as shown in the system boundaries for the LCC battery pack in Figure 17.

Figure 17 System boundaries for the battery pack LCC calculation using the BatPaC tool

The BatPaC model has been developed at Argonne National Laboratory for lithium-ion battery packs used in automotive transportation. The parameters in the design model are for specified power, energy, and type of vehicle battery. The cost of the designed battery is then calculated by accounting for every step in the lithium-ion battery manufacturing process. BatPaC is the only publicly available model of which we are aware that performs a bottom-up lithium-ion battery design and cost calculation. BatPaC methods to design Li-ion batteries for electric-drive vehicles based on modelling with Microsoft® Office Excel spreadsheets. The original model and manual were publicly peer-reviewed by battery experts assembled by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency [48]. In this report, the explanation of the BatPaC excel spreadsheet is not included, as it can be looked up the manual of this tool [48].

The LCC reported here follows the structured as shown Equation 1 (section 1.2) , adapted to the system boundaries and scope of this baseline assessment aligned with the cradle-to-gate approach. Therefore, the adapted equation that will be used is:

$$LCC = \frac{MCC+CPCR}{BES} \quad (2)$$

Where:

LCC: Life Cycle Costing of battery (Excluding the externalities), \$/kWh

MCC: Cell material/Component cost (that include the costs of the raw materials for the cells and the non-cells components, including the BMS, the thermal management unit), \$

CPCR: Cell production cost (that include the cost of manufacturing and assembling of all the components, including indirect costs, labour costs and material rejection and recycling costs), \$

BES: Battery energy storage, kWh

It should be noted that the units of cost parameters to calculate the LCC are defined in US \$. This choice is due to the fact that the current raw materials and commodities that are used in the production of LiB are traded in the international market, where US \$ is the currency that is commonly used.

After verification, we have found that the cost parameters defined in sections 2 and 3 (for both their materials and their manufacturing and assembling) are aligned with the ones managed by the BatPac to assess the battery pack, which means the reasonable use of this tool with our model, raised in Equation 2 to evaluate the base line of the battery in terms of costs. Those BatPac cost parameters are as follows:

- Cost of the raw materials and their production for the cells compositions (anode, cathode, separators, electrolyte...)
- Cost of the raw materials and the components production for the non-cell materials such as modules elements, connectors,
- Cost of the raw materials and the components production for the battery pack casing and connectors
- Cost of the thermal unit
- Cost of the control module/BMS
- Material rejection and recycling costs

4.2.2 How does the BatPaC work?

As stated above, the LCC has been supported by the use of background data coming from literature and BatPaC tool, that contains information on cost of different elements of LiB batteries and it is aligned with the calculation methodology that has been adopted in this analysis. In BatPaC tool, the manufactured cost of a battery pack is calculated with input from the design

information generated in modelling the cell and battery pack performance. The manufacturing cost is then added to these materials costs, along with a warranty cost, to reach the unit cost of a single battery pack. The manufacturing costs for the designed battery are scaled from a baseline plant. The baseline plant was designed for a battery of intermediate size and production rate so as to establish a centre-point for other plants. The baseline plant accounts for the size, speed, number of units, direct labour, and depreciation of the capital cost for each processing step. These costs are adjusted to meet the requirements for a plant producing the battery under study. The process expenses are summed with the additional costs of operating the manufacturing facility. These costs include launch costs, working capital, variable overhead, general sales administration (GSA), research and development, depreciation, warranty, and profit. Additionally, the costs for the thermal management, battery management system, and disconnects have been estimated to provide the total cost to the OEM for the integrated battery pack. The baseline plant produces 100,000 EV battery packs per year with 60-kWh energy and 220-kW power. However, for this assessment, a baseline plant that produces 50,000 EV batteries a year has been considered as it reflects best the current situation. The plant costs are evaluated at our estimates of present-day unit costs for materials, labour, and capital and plant area [49].

Various cell and battery design concepts are under development at battery manufacturers. According to the literature research presented in section 2, the exact design of the battery does not have an important effect on the cost for a set cell chemistry system; the amounts of electrode materials and the number, capacity and electrode area of the cells, are the determining cost factors. The most common cell designs for batteries in large-scale production are cylindrical wound cells, flat wound cells, and prismatic cells with flat plates. Cylindrical cells probably have a slight advantage for the assembly of the electrode-separator unit because of the ease of making a cylindrical winding.

This is why the results calculated by BatPaC provide a full assessment of the cells and active materials costs of a battery with the same chemistry and capacity that the Audi e-Tron here assessed, have been considered as an excellent approach to what the real cost of this Audi battery.

4.2.3 Inventory for the LCC calculation

Following the request by the user in the BatPaC tool, we have introduced the inputs regarding the specifications of NMC-622 chemistry LiB aligned with the characteristics of the Audi e-Tron battery described in section 3. These inputs are classified in three categories, namely, chemistry, battery pack design and EV charging as shown in **Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia..**

shows the unit costs related to the materials used in the tool. We have decided to use these costs as default since the costs for the battery pack are expected to decrease in the next years (see Figure 7). Therefore, materials costs should not increase considering that large volume of production of LIB packs and the technology development are the major drivers to the production cost decrease.

Table 11 Unit costs used in the BatPaC model

Costs	
Positive Electrode, \$/kg	
Active material	20.60
Carbon	6.60
Binder	9.50
Solvent (NMP)	3.10
Negative electrode, \$/kg	
Active material	12.50
Carbon Black	6.60
Binder	10.00
Solvent (Water)	0.00
Al Foil	0.30 (\$/m ²)
Cu Foil	1.20 (\$/m ²)
Separator	1.10 (\$/m ²)
Electrolyte	15.00 (\$/L)

The use of these unit costs are used in the battery pack design which cost calculation in BatPaC represents projections for up to ten years in the future.

Table 12 Inputs for the LCC inventory required by the BatPaC tool

Inputs	Quantity	Units
Chemistry: NMC622-G		
Positive electrode	Li_{1.05}(Ni_{0.6}Mn_{0.2}Co_{0.2})_{0.95}O₂	
Positive active material specific capacity	180	mAh/g
Void volume fraction	25	%
Positive foil thickness	25*	µm
Maximum positive electrode thickness	120	µm
Negative electrode	Graphite	
Negative active material specific capacity	360	mAh/g
N/P capacity ratio after formation	1.10	---
Void volume fraction	25	%
Negative current collector thickness	15*	µm
Separator thickness	25*	µm
Maximum charging current density	9	mA/cm ²
Battery pack design		
Coolant type	Ethylene glycol/water (EG-W) 50% / 50%	
Calculate fast charging?	Yes	
Target battery pack power at 20% SOC	350	kW
Number of cells per module (total)	12	---
Number of cells in parallel group in module	12	---
Number of modules in row	18	---
Number of rows of modules per pack	2	---
Number of modules in parallel	2	---
Number of packs manufactured per year	50,000	---

Energy requirement for a UDDS cycle	300	Wh/mile
Vehicle range pack energy	95.0	kWh
Useable battery energy	91	% of total (EV)
EV charging		
Time to recharge from 15% to 75% SOC, min	9.65	min

(*) Values manipulated in the BatPaC iteration process to fit the weight to the Audi-e Tron battery pack.

4.2.4 Overall LCC results

According to the data introduced in BatPaC model, the overall results related to the battery parameters and unit costs are shown in Table 13. Input parameters associated with the battery non-active parts (thickness of positive foil, negative current collector and separator) were adjusted through an iterative process, in order to meet the characteristics of the battery with a weight of 643 kg close to the Audi-e Tron battery pack (700 kg).

It can be observed that the cost of OEM or battery pack itself is \$14,834. Considering the vehicle range pack energy (95 kWh), we can say that the LCC is around 156 \$/kWh. Nevertheless, considering the useable battery energy (91%), the real LCC is by 172 \$/kWh. From the BatPaC tool, the OEM cost is subjected to an error of price percentage for battery pack. For unit materials and processing costs, the error is $\pm 10\%$ and $\pm 5\%$ for electrode thickness and capacity limits. Therefore, it can be said the real LCC of 172 \$/kWh is consistent with what we disclosed in section 2.2 (156 €/kWh).

Table 13 Overall results in terms of battery specifications and costs gotten from BatPaC tool

Specification or cost	Quantities	Units
Battery system total energy storage	95	kWh
Required battery system power	350	kW
Pack power to energy ratio	4	---
Pack charging time for 80% Δ SOC	35	min
Positive electrode thickness	43	μ m
Positive electrode areal capacity	3	mAh/cm ²
Negative electrode areal capacity	3	mAh/cm ²
Cell capacity	59	Ah
Module mass	14	kg
Number of cells per pack	432	---
Nominal battery system voltage (OCV at 50% SOC)	68	V
Cost of pack to original equipment manufacturer (OEM)	14,834	\$
Pack total mass	643	kg
Pack volume	320	L
Total cost of cells	118	\$/kWh
Cost of cells	139	\$/kWhUse
Extra cost of meeting fast charging requirement	2,979	\$
Production volume	50,000	Packs per year
Cell cost to OEM	26	US\$/Cell

Other cost results are also provided in Table 13, such as the total cell costs that is 118 \$/kWh and equivalent to 100€/kWh when using a currency rate corresponding to July 2021. This is also consistent with the cell cost reported in section 2.2 ranging between 82 and 96 €/kWh for 2017 and 2020 respectively.

In order to have additional information about the calculated parameters and costs, the following subsections present a breakdown of the them. This can help us to identify the costing hotspots in this LCC analysis along the life cycle stage similar the procedure when applying the LCA methodology.

4.2.5 Breakdown results

The breakdown costs by battery system are shown in Table 14 in absolute values. The cells represent a cost of \$11,199 (around 75% of the total battery pack cost). It is in line with the cost percentage reported in literature (section 2.2), where the battery production costs (electrode production and cell finishing) are the main contributors in the life cycle of battery. The next costly systems are the pack hardware, wiring and the BMS, which are much less than the cells.

As known, the MARBEL project aims to design, develop and demonstrate new modular, compact, lightweight and high-performance battery packs together with flexible and robust battery management systems for BEV and PHEV. The chemistry of the active materials involved in the developed batteries will not be addressed in the project. According to the overall results from BatPaC (Figure 19), the material costs are the most representative in the battery pack lifecycle stage (around 57%). On the other hand, the costs of active positive plus negative materials (both of them as the chemistry part of the battery), represent the 42% of the material and purchased costs. Therefore, results from this baseline LCC study suggest us that the strategy for cost reduction should be focussed on the rest of other materials related to the battery jacket, module hardware, separators, the BMS and thermal management system linked to the modular design. This will help to complement the environmental results conducted from the LCA study in previous section.

Table 15, Table 16 and Table 17 shown in detail the calculated parameters, costs for materials and other items (grouped by categories) considering the battery production at plant level.

Table 14 Absolute costs by systems of the battery pack

Subsystem	Contents	Cost (\$)
Cells		11,199
Additions at module level		
Module hardware	Housing, thermal conductors, terminals	831
CSC	Cell-to-cell balancing, sensors, and low-voltage wiring	344
Addition at pack level		
Pack hardware	Tray, compression structure, housing	1,647
Thermal management system	Heaters, coolant	180
High voltage wiring	Bussing between modules, and pack terminals	227.0
BMU & Disconnects	Battery management, module balancing, 2-way comm	366
Total Battery pack(s)		14,794
Exterior cooling system	Additions to AC for thermal management	40
Total including cooling system		14,834

For easier visualization, an overall cost breakdown pie in terms of percentage for the life cycle stage \$/pack is shown in Figure 18, where the materials and purchased items are the most contributors (76%), being the cost of materials 2.5 times than the total purchased item cost.

Figure 18 Overall cost breakdown of battery pack. Calculated from BatPaC tool

The dominant contribution of material cost is also observed when looking the results through life cycle stage (materials, purchased items and the manufacturing process), such as shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19 Results by lifecycle stage (cradle-to-gate approach), including overhead

Moreover, it can be observed that the cost of manufacturing is around 20% of the battery system, where the cost of activities associated with electrode processing, cost of cell assembly, cost for formation cycling, testing and sealing are the more presentative steps (18%).

Since the cost of materials influences significantly on the LCC of battery pack, it is interesting to figure out which is the contribution of the different materials and components making battery up. In this sense, Figure 20 shows the contribution percentage of material/components. The positive active material shows to have the higher cost (31%), followed by the battery jacket (17%), separators (12%), the negative active material (11%), and both the negative current collector plus module hardware (16%).

Figure 20 Materials and purchased costs break-down

Table 15 Detailed calculated parameters, costs for materials, and another items to produce battery packs at plant level

Category classification	Quantities	Units
Calculated battery parameters		
Vehicle electric range	269	miles
Number of battery packs	1	---
Number of cells per pack	432	---
Number of modules per pack	36	----
Battery system total energy storage	95.0	kWh
Cell capacity	58.9	Ah
Nominal battery system voltage (OCV at 50% SOC)	67.5	V
Battery system power at target % OCV	1361.5	kW
Target % OCV at full power		%
% OCV at full power adjusted for thickness limit	80	%
Battery system volume (all packs, with cooling)	95.7	L
Battery system weight (all packs, with cooling)	322.8	kg
Cooling system power requirement	649.8	W
Materials and purchased items summary		
Cost of positive active material	3,402.07	\$/pack
Cost of negative active material	1,169.42	\$/pack
Cost of carbon black	74.12	\$/pack
Cost of positive current collector	207.56	\$/pack
Cost of negative current collector	870.99	\$/pack
Cost of separators	1,346.91	\$/pack
Cost of electrolyte	686.86	\$/pack
Cost of cell hardware	431.72	\$/pack
Cost of module hardware	872.24	\$/pack
Cost of battery jacket	1,855.62	\$/pack
Total cost of materials and purchased items	10,917.50	\$/pack
Cost of battery management system	366.03	\$/pack
Cost of thermal management system	40.00	\$/pack
Direct labour summary		
Direct labour: electrode processing	278,794	h/year
Direct labour: cell assembly	229,532	h/year
Direct labour: formation cycling, testing and sealing	91,748	h/year
Direct labour: module and battery assembly, hrs/year	150,271	h/year
Direct labour: cell and materials rejection and recycling	8,917	h/year
Direct labour: receiving and shipping	85,921	h/year
Direct labour: control laboratory	51,250	h/year
Total direct labour	896,434	h/year
Capital equipment summary		
Capital equipment: electrode processing	55	\$millions
Capital equipment: cell assembly	40	\$millions
Capital equipment: formation cycling, testing and sealing	70	\$millions
Capital equipment: module and battery assembly	27	\$millions
Capital equipment: cell and materials rejection and recycling	2	\$millions

Table 16 Detailed calculated parameter, costs for materials, and another items to produce battery packs at plant level (continuation)

Category classification	Quantities	Units
Capital equipment summary		
Capital equipment: receiving and shipping	24	\$millions
Capital equipment: control laboratory	4	\$millions
Total cost of capital equipment	222,81	\$millions
Building, land utilities		
Building: electrode processing, m ²	7,189	m ²
Building: cell assembly, m ²	5,204	m ²
Building: formation cycling, testing and sealing, m ²	4,045	m ²
Building: module and battery assembly	2,535	m ²
Building: cell and materials rejection and recycling	939	m ²
Building: receiving and shipping	3,597	m ²
Building: control laboratory	435	m ²
Total building, land and utilities area	23,943	m ²
Cost multipliers for overhead to basic cost factors		
Direct labour summary with overhead		
Electrode processing	260.18	\$/pack
Cell assembly	214.21	\$/pack
Formation cycling, testing and sealing	85.62	\$/pack
Module and battery assembly	140.24	\$/pack
Cell and materials rejection and recycling	8.32	\$/pack
Receiving and shipping	80.19	\$/pack
Control laboratory	47.83	\$/pack
Total cost of direct labour with overhead	836.59	\$/pack
Capital equipment with overhead		\$/pack
Electrode processing	429.80	\$/pack
Cell assembly	309.48	\$/pack
Formation cycling, testing and sealing	545.52	\$/pack
Module and battery assembly	209.72	\$/pack
Cell and materials rejection and recycling	14.40	\$/pack
Receiving and shipping	185.57	\$/pack
Control laboratory	32,92	\$/pack
Total	1,727.41	\$/pack
Building, land and utilities with overhead		
Electrode processing	66.11	\$/pack
Cell assembly	47.85	\$/pack
Formation cycling, testing and sealing	37.20	\$/pack
Module and battery assembly	23.31	\$/pack
Cell and materials rejection and recycling	8.63	\$/pack
Receiving and shipping	33.07	\$/pack

Table 17 Detailed calculated parameter, costs for materials, and another items to produce battery packs at plant level (continuation)

Category classification	Quantities	Units
Building, land and utilities with overhead (Continuation)		
Control laboratory	4.00	---
Total cost of direct labour with overhead	220.16	---
Cost breakdown with overhead distributed to processes		
Cost of materials	8,274	\$
Cost of purchased items	3,370	\$
Cost of manufacturing		
Cost of electrode processing	756	\$
Cost of cell assembly	572	\$
Cost of formation cycling, testing and sealing	668	\$
Cost of module and battery assembly	373	\$
Cost of cell and materials rejection and recycling	31	\$
Cost of receiving and shipping	299	\$
Cost of control laboratory	85	\$
Total manufacturing cost	2,784	\$
Battery pack total	14,428	\$
Pack integration (BMS & disconnects)	366	\$
Estimated cost to OEM for thermal management	40	\$
Total cost to OEM for complete battery system	14,834.35	\$

As known, the MARBEL project aims to design, develop and demonstrate new modular, compact, lightweight and high-performance battery packs together with flexible and robust battery management systems for BEV and PHEV. The chemistry of the active materials involved in the developed batteries will not be addressed in the project. According to the overall results from BatPaC (Figure 19), the material costs are the most representative in the battery pack lifecycle stage (around 57%). On the other hand, the costs of active positive plus negative materials (both of them as the chemistry part of the battery), represent the 42% of the material and purchased costs. Therefore, results from this baseline LCC study suggest us that the strategy for cost reduction should be focussed on the rest of other materials related to the battery jacket, module hardware, separators, the BMS and thermal management system linked to the modular design. This will help to complement the environmental results conducted from the LCA study in previous section.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In order to meet the task 8.1 objectives, an environmental and economic preliminary evaluation was conducted in this report to describe the MARBEL baseline scenario. For such evaluation, simplified life cycle studies were performed following Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology and other guidelines (ILCD Handbook and SETAC recommendations for Life Cycle Costing (LCC)).

MARBEL battery pack will be compared to the 95kWh (around 84 kWh useable) Audi e-Tron 55 BP considered as the baseline scenario for the life cycle studies. To define the goal and scope for these studies, IREC and EURECAT performed an intensive investigation from scientific literature where it was detected that the majority of studies apply their own impact assessment methodology varying significantly from the scope and system boundaries. Different approaches are often used, such as the cradle-to-gate and cradle-to-grave. Another factor that influences on the different studies is the reliance on the LCI data, commonly coming from existent publications when lacking.

The LCI data, goal and scope must be aligned to produce comprehensive LCA/LCC results. Based on the above and the early stage of the project in which this deliverable is performed, the available data were those related to the first life cycle stages of the battery, involving the raw materials extraction, battery cell and module production and assembly process with the energy, material and cost flows involved. Therefore, a scope cradle-to-gate subjected the source of available data was chosen to do the preliminary LCA and LCC studies.

In this line, the main conclusions are listed as follows:

LCA baseline scenario:

In the present study a NMC-622 battery pack has been assessed in order to determine the main hotspots. From that, the main conclusions extracted are:

- Cathode is the main contribution to the production of the battery. Since MARBEL project is not focused on the chemistry of the battery, this aspect is not foreseen to be tackled during the project. Nevertheless, second life applications will decrease the allocated impacts of production phase.
- Housing of the battery causes the main impacts of non-cell components. Hence, improvement on the design of this component is able to potentially decrease the environmental impacts of the battery pack. Furthermore, second life applications will also decrease the impact of the non-cell components.
- This study is aimed at the production phase, and hence, it is foreseen that the environmental performance of MARBEL could improve a little bit against baseline technology. However, the main improvements in terms of environmental gains of MARBEL will be deployed during use phase, due to technical performance will allow better efficiency.

LCC baseline scenario:

-The cost for the battery pack is around \$14,834 and considering the vehicle range pack energy (95 kWh), the LCC is around 156 \$/kWh. Nevertheless, considering the useable battery energy (91%), the real LCC is by 172 \$/kWh, which is consistent with cost found in literature.

-Overall cost breakdown results referred to \$/pack shown that the materials and purchased items are the main contributors in the LCC, 57% and 23% of contribution respectively.

- The contribution percentage of material/components is distributed to the positive active material with the higher cost (31%), flowed by the battery jacket (17%), separators (12%), the negative active material (11%), and both the negative current collector plus module hardware (16%).

Results from this baseline LCC study suggest that, considering the objectives of the MARBEL project, the strategy for cost reduction should be focussed on materials related to the battery jacket, module hardware, separators, the BMS and thermal management system linked to the modular design. Acting on the battery's active materials (less expensive materials and production costs) can also bring benefits, but the development of new chemistries, especially for the cathode, is beyond the scope of the project.

The baseline scenario defined by the NMC 622 battery of the Audi5 e-Tron has been characterized from an environmental and economic perspective, using LCA and LCC methodologies with a cradle to gate approach. The results here presented could be fine-tuned due to the inclusion of more accurate data and the assessment of the use phase and the end of life phase. This improvement would be carried out considering the next LCA and LCC activities expected in the MARBEL project in WP8.

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